

Whose Financial Grievances Go Unobserved?*

18th September 2023

Abstract

Financial inclusion around the world is developing rapidly and reaching 76% of the world's population. However, the gap between access to formal financial products and the long-term use of them remains. We present the results of a first representative telephone survey in India, which explores a major friction that creates this gap: Redressing consumer complaints. Consumer complaints behaviour is product-invariant. Conditional on a grievance, vulnerable consumer groups such as the poor and low-educated are significantly less likely to complain owing to lack of procedural knowledge and belief that resolution is unlikely. They go unobserved in the official data. At the minimum, policy steps to address this friction will require a large-scale overhaul of the current grievance redress framework to be consumer-focused and stop assuming consumers have the educational, means and faith to resolve their complaints.

*We thank the Editor Shiyi Chen and two anonymous referees for their valuable and constructive suggestions in improving this paper. All remaining errors are our own. All authors have no declaration of interests. Corresponding Author: Renuka Sane, Associate Professor, National Institute of Public Finance and Policy, New Delhi. Address: 18/2 Satsang Vihar Marg, Special Institutional Area, New Delhi 100067. renukas@gmail.com.

1 Introduction

Global progress on financial inclusion has been truly successful. In the 2021 representative survey on financial inclusion, covering 128,000 adults in 123 economies, Demirgüç-Kunt et al. (2022) document that worldwide ownership of a bank account has reached 76% (71% in developing countries). In India, the share of adults with no bank account dropped from 47% in 2014 to 22% in 2021, summarising the rapid progress made in access to formal financial products and markets across the income distribution. However, only about 35% of all adults used these bank accounts to store money for cash management in the past year (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2022). Recent work by Morgan and Long (2020) show that financial literacy alone cannot formalise savings as those with higher financial literacy are more likely to save in both formal and informal forms even after accounting for income and education. The most natural progression in this goal of formalising financial savings and investment is for policies to reduce potential frictions that result in such a large gap between access and use of financial products.

While large strides have been made in enabling access to finance, underlying systems to enable sustained use have remained by and large unchanged. For instance, consumer financial protection, the world over, has become a core function for regulators in financial markets. One aspect of consumer protection regulation is handling customer complaints. Analysing consumer complaints is important to not only evaluate the functioning of the consumer complaints mechanism, but also because it provides useful feedback for policy on engendering sustained use of formal financial products. For example, complaints about Payment Protection Insurance (PPI) between 2006 and 2011 to the Financial Ombudsman Service in the UK played an important role in uncovering the mis-selling scandal and reshaping policy on PPI (Ferran, 2012). A growing body of research focus on studying complaints data with agencies that handle consumer complaints (for example, the Consumer Financial Protection Bureau or CFPB in the US), as well as methods of resolution used by such agencies (Ayers et al., 2014; Cheng et al., 2016; Doyle et al., 2014; Foohey, 2017; Littwin, 2015).

In developing economies, where such large gaps between access and use persist, grievance redress systems remain antiquated and cater to rich, well-informed consumers. All financial regulators in India mention consumer protection in their regulations, and have some consumer *grievance redress mechanism* (GRM) in place. However, a recent body of work in India suggests that the current framework has much room for improvement (Balasub-

ramaniam, Sane et al., 2022; Balasubramaniam et al., 2020; Raghavan & Shah, 2020; Sane et al., 2021). A comparison of the grievance redress management (GRM) systems set up by Indian regulators against international benchmarks finds that the *design* of the grievance redress mechanism has many shortcomings (Gulati & Suresh, 2022).

One of the reasons for limited research on consumer complaints in India and the consumer characteristics around who face grievances and who use the complaint system is the lack of a public database that provides information on the grievances that make it to the system. A database of complaints, even when it is available, provides information only on those grievances that translate into complaints. The true extent of grievances are always likely to be higher than those reported in official statistics. More importantly, such aggregate data does not contain consumer characteristics – a feature important to learn about the nature of consumers whose grievances reach the formal system and those who choose not to complain.

In this paper, we establish the first systematic evidence through a representative survey in the National Capital Region (NCR) region in India, on the extent of grievances in retail financial markets alongside a rich set of consumer characteristics.¹ We then explore evidence on the type of grievances, consumer characteristics that choose not to complain, and the reasons why some consumers do not complain. We examine the nature of frictions that prevent consumers from lodging a complaint. We distinguish between the type of friction and consumer demographic characteristics and suggest that the type of friction faced by different types of consumers are heterogeneous.

Previewing the results, we find that official estimates of complaints under-report total grievances by 60-80 times. That is for every complaint on banking and payments that makes it to the regulatory system, there are 60 grievances that do not get reported. For every official complaint on insurance there are 88 complaints that do not get recorded. Grievances in banking and payment mostly pertain to “transaction issues” such as delays in payments, and technology malfunction. Grievances in insurance, however, often pertain to “non transaction issues” such as mis-selling and fraud. In a frictionless world consumers have an incentive to file a complaint when financial products fail to deliver. However, in reality, we find that very few of them do so.

On the one hand, vulnerable groups such as the poor and the uneducated have lower

¹The National Capital Region around Delhi, India covers an area of 13,183 square miles, and is home to about 40-50 million people.

incidence of grievances, principally due to differences in the frequency with which they interact with the system. However, conditional on facing complaints, those in vulnerable groups (with low education and low assets) are less likely to voice their complaints, and more likely to not have enough information about the redress procedure – a finding that directly has important policy implications for the design of a modern GRM. On the other hand, consumers with high levels of education and income hold strong ex-ante beliefs that the likelihood of a favourable resolution is low and that their costs of complaining are high, thus resulting in requiring them to undertake a high-cost, low-success exercise.

This paper contributes to the growing body of literature on citizen-state relationship in economics (Robinson, 2015; Sharan & Kumar, 2019). Complaints are seen as “claims on the state for social welfare goods and services” (Kruks-Wisner, 2018), and a means through which citizens are able to negotiate their relationship with the state. While financial products reflect contractual relationships that are different from that with the state, there are similarities on the question of what drives people to “make a claim”. This becomes important as a vast number of Indian households enter formal finance. In order to sustain participation in, and enable the efficient use of financial markets by households, a two-fold approach is required. First, there is a need for generating meaningful data on consumer experiences with financial products, and grievance redress frameworks while they interact with retail financial products and sales practices. This will enable an understanding of how the current system works, and whether it can be scaled from a banked population of 300 million it currently serves to over a billion Indians it will be expected to serve. Second, there is a need for a contextualised learning of what the principles and design of a grievance redress system that needs to cater to more than a billion Indians ought to look like. This paper also contributes to the growing literature on the importance of regulatory reforms in India (Bose, Filomeni & Mallick, 2021) as it keeps pace with the rapidly shifting reality of its economy.

Section 2 presents an overview of the grievance redress mechanisms in India and the official statistics on grievances. Section 3 presents the study design, and summary statistics from our survey. Section 5 presents our main findings related to frictions in the process between facing a grievance to filing a complaint and obtaining a resolution. Section 6 concludes with forward-looking policy suggestions.

2 Background: Grievance redress in financial markets in India

Indian financial markets are siloed into four broad segments: banking and payments regulated by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), securities markets by the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI), insurance regulated by the Insurance Development Authority of India (IRDAI), and pensions by the Pension Fund and Regulatory Development Authority of India (PFRDA). Each regulator runs its own grievance redress system - either in the form of an Ombudsman (in the case of banking, insurance and pensions) or an online complaints management system (called SCORES in the case of securities markets).² Table 1 provides a brief description of the number of complaints received by each of the regulators.

Insert Table 1 here.

Reported statistics suggest that the incidence of grievances in India is relatively low. For example, official statistics suggest that in 2019-2020, there were about 2 lakh complaints related to banking across the whole of the country, and given the prevalence of banking, this amounted to an incidence of 0.01%.

Taken at face value, these statistics suggest that the incidence of grievances in India are low, and there are no concerns at all. However, anecdotal evidence suggests that these numbers do not provide a complete picture of grievances in India for various reasons. First, these numbers do not capture grievances that get resolved by the financial service providers. The current system requires that the consumer first file a complaint with the Financial Service Provider (FSP). If the FSP does not act within a given time-frame, or does not resolve the complaint to the satisfaction of the customer, the consumer escalate the complaint to the Ombudsman or SCORES as the case may be. The numbers reported by the regulators are those that were escalated after having gone through the FSP. Second, these numbers are likely to be an understatement as not all grievances make it to complaints. Consumers may not complain to the FSP in the first place, or get dissuaded by their experience at the FSP to not escalate further.

Our paper aims to capture the lifecycle of a grievance faced by a consumer, and then seek to understand whether the complaint rates observed by the regulator are small because it is the ground reality or because of frictions associated with resolving a grievance. We

²Gulati and Suresh, 2022 study the structure and policy apparatus of redress systems of financial regulators and describe the shortcomings of the current system.

describe our research design below.

3 Research Design

Our research involves two stages. First, we deploy a state-of-the-art telephone assisted survey instrument to capture details of formal access to financial products, and the grievances associated with it. The survey also goes into learning about various stages between a grievance and a complaint, including resolution.

3.1 Sampling design

The analysis on representative incidence measurement uses data from a representative telephone survey of 4,544 individuals conducted in Delhi-NCR. We used probability-weighted random digit dialling (RDD) to construct the sampling frame of individuals to call and conduct interviews. In this sampling method, we made use of mobile numbers patterns in India’s telecommunications network. In India, each telecom service provider for each geographical circle is allotted a five-digit number series by the Department of Telecommunications (DOT) which they are allowed to use at beginning of the 10 digit phone numbers they sell. To create a list of N phone numbers, all the five-digit number series assigned to all telecom service providers in Delhi circle by DOT were taken in equal proportion.³

To this, randomly generated 5 digits were added to create 10 digit mobile numbers. Then an auto-dialer software was created and used to validate the phone numbers. This validation process identifies active phone numbers. We generate 230,000 possible 10-digit phone numbers, and then processed each number up to three times through an auto-dialer software to identify active numbers. This provided 48,000 available numbers to conduct interviews. Interviewers conducted the calls in a random order resulting in a total of 5029 successful calls. We interviewed adults who were at least 21 years old and owned at least one of the five financial products: Banking, Payments, Insurance, Securities and Pensions. Unless the respondent fulfilled this criterion, they were not interviewed. We use 4,544 observations that successfully pass our validation checks and have no missing observations on demographics for analysis. This approach is new to developing countries and pioneered in Coffey et al. (2021).

³The number series are publicly available on Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI) website

3.2 Representativeness and External Validity

Appendix Figures [A.1](#), [A.2](#), [A.3](#) and [A.4](#) compares sample distribution of age, highest education, household size, family annual income with population estimates from the Consumer Pyramids Household Survey (CPHS) database for the same region. Although our sample is representative of household size and education, it fails to capture the right tail of population income distribution and older population. If young and poor consumers are likely to face greater grievances because of inexperience with the formal system, then our estimates are likely upward biased, taking us closer to the observed complaint rates at the regulator, thus a more conservative estimate of the true magnitude of the problem at hand. While it is true that our survey captures more of the young, and the poor, it is important to note that this is necessary especially in the context of future-proofing sustained use of formal finance, and from the context of policy design that enables even the poorest to make use of grievance redress systems.

We note here that the grievance redress framework in place is a pan-Indian framework. However, we only measure incidence from our survey from NCR, Delhi, India. The composition of financial consumers in the NCR is no different from other financial consumers across India, in that, NCR is a heterogeneous mixture of population across the income, age, gender and wealth distribution in India. This study has its inherent limitation of not being externally valid across sub-populations unobserved in sample that may be prevalent in other parts of India. However, Balasubramaniam, Gawali, Sane and Sharma (2022) find that the incidence rates are broadly similar in five other Indian states – an exercise that is reassuring that measurement error and selection are not entirely driving our findings.

3.3 Survey instrument

The survey instrument consists of six modules. These ask questions on demographics, awareness on regulators and GRM, usage of financial products and incidence of grievances, reaction to these grievances, inherent intention to complain and their experiences with existing GRM.

We begin the interview with a scenario question to measure consumer’s intention to complain. We ask about their awareness of regulators and various GRMs. After this, we ask about the access to various financial products and whether they have faced grievances with these products. We then document their responses to these grievances. If they mention that they complained to service providers and regulators, we then document their exper-

ience of engaging with them. If they inform us that they did not complain, we elicit the reasons for not complaining. It ends by asking questions on demographics. A detailed description of the instrument and its modules is given in Appendix Table A.I.

Considering the paucity of time in telephonic surveys, in case a respondent shared that they had grievances with multiple financial products, we dig deep into the nature of the grievance, their responses and their interaction with GRM for only one financial product. For each financial product, a separate module was created to capture these details. Assignment of the module of a particular financial product was not random. Financial products that have low penetration such as pensions, securities were given higher weightage. For instance, the conditional probability of assignment of 'securities' module, when consumer faced grievances with securities, pensions and banking is 0.5. The complete set of conditional probabilities is given in Appendix Table A.II.⁴

3.4 Pilots and training

Two rounds of pilot calls were done to finalise the instrument and interview administration and data collection were on a computer assisted, and automated. Two rounds of training were conducted for interviewers. The training was provided not only on the instrument and how to administer certain questions but also on the subject matter. It was relevant that they understood the basics of financial products we covered and the existing grievance redress mechanism in the Indian financial sector. Several rounds of mock calls were conducted to train the surveyors and test the CAPI software. On average, each interview took around 15 minutes.

3.5 Estimation

Our interest is in understanding the role that income, assets and education play in determining complaints. These characteristics are important because they tell us whether relatively more “vulnerable” populations are less likely to access the formal grievance redress system.

We model the log odds of having a grievance and making a complaint using binary regres-

⁴The survey instrument in English and Hindi is available here: <https://www.dropbox.com/s/m8mkolng8jiukug/PhoneSurveyInstrument.pdf?dl=0>.

sion with a logit link function and robust error variance, given as:

$$\log \frac{\pi_i}{(1 - \pi_i)} = \beta_0 + \beta X_i + T$$

where $\frac{\pi_i}{(1 - \pi_i)}$ is the odds that a grievance (and a complaint) for individual $i = 1$, 0 otherwise. β_0 represents the log odds of having a grievance (or reporting a complaint) for the reference category. βX_i represents the change in the log odds of the outcome for a one unit change in the vector of household characteristics (age, sex and education, income and asset quintiles). We also control for whether the grievance is with respect to a “transaction” or “non-transaction” related issue (T). The odds of an event is the ratio of the probability of the event happening to the probability of not happening (i.e. $\frac{p}{1-p}$).

We might expect that those in low income households are unable to navigate the financial system and are at a disadvantage when complaining about financial products. For instance, Heese and Pérez-Cavazos (2021) show the importance of reducing retaliation costs to tap into employees’ knowledge of misconduct.

We then perform certain counterfactual calculations for one canonical individual. We focus on an individual in the 41-54 age group, with a salaried job, a household size of 3-5 members, and a non-transaction related grievance. We then vary the education, assets and income of this person to see the variation in the probability of complaint.

4 Data and summary statistics

Table 2 describes the data for the phone survey. We see that sample is predominately young with 66% of individuals who have completed at least senior secondary education. The majority of them either have salaried jobs in the private sector or are self-employed. 82% of them reported annual income less than 3 lakhs per annum.

Table 2 here

In terms of participation in financial markets, 97% reported having at least a bank account. Under banking services, 81% of the sample reported having a chequebook or ATM card, 39% reported using online or phone banking and 14% had taken any bank loan. Around 51% reported using payment apps. 20% of the individuals has some kind of life insurance plan and 5% had invested in securities and mutual fund markets. 4% of the sample reported having pension products.

4.1 The incidence of grievances

Table 3 shows the incidence of grievances in our sample. We find that as a percentage of the total users of the product, the largest incidence of grievances is in payments followed by banking. 17% of those who use payment services in the NCR region had a grievance, compared to only 9% in banking and 4% in insurance.⁵ While these may look small in percentage terms, as a proportion of the total users of products, this can easily translate into lakhs of customers facing a problem.

Table 3 here

There is considerable variation in the frequency of grievances. A large proportion (62%) of those who had a grievance with their banking product, had only one-two issues in the last one year, relative to payments where almost 35% of users had over five grievances in the last one year. This may also be a consequence of more frequent use of payments during the year.

There are two ways of looking at grievances - those that involve problems in transactions, and those that involve instances of poor sales practices or outright fraud. The former are relatively benign and can be resolved through improvements in processes. The latter are more challenging because they involve misbehaviour by the staff of financial service providers, and suggest that regulation is broken. We categorise the various grievances of consumers into those that pertain to transactions and those that are not related to transactions. It is useful to remember that grievances are consumer perceptions of what is not working, and need not necessarily reflect the exact problem. For example, a consumer may think that high charges were deducted and this is a transaction related issue. However, it might be that in reality the FSP may have misled the consumer to believing that no charges would be deducted.

Table 4 here

Table 4 provides the broad breakup of the nature of grievances across the three products. When it comes to payments, grievances are mostly about failures in transactions - such as money being debited after transaction failures, or not receiving cashbacks. In the case of insurance, there is a much greater proportion of misselling and fraud. This includes direct complaints of misselling or outright fraud. These show serious lapses of behaviour by the

⁵Given the relatively small access to securities and pensions products, we do not focus on these going forward.

staff of banking and insurance companies.⁶

4.2 From grievances to complaints

The question of interest is the number of grievances that actually get translated to complaints, and the number of complaints that actually get resolved. In Table 5 we present the lifecycle of grievances in the financial sector in our sample. The first two columns reproduce the statistics presented in Table 3 - the number of people who had access to the product in our sample, and the number who had a grievance with the product. Because people may own multiple products, we randomly picked a particular product and asked detailed questions on complaint behaviour for that product. This is evident from column (3). For example, of the 388 people who had a grievance related to banking, 256 were asked detailed questions on actual complaints.

Table 5 here

In the case of banking we find that about 55% of those who had a grievance complained to the financial service provider (FSP). Of these, 38% were not able to find adequate resolution. There is a big drop in escalating further to the Ombudsman - only 5% of those who had not found resolution escalated to the Banking Ombudsman. In the case of payments as well, of those who had a grievance, only 50% complained to the financial service provider. Relative to banking, a larger proportion who complained about payment (78%) got resolution with the FSP. Only 1% of those who did not get a resolution with the FSP complained to the Ombudsman, and also got a resolution. In the case of insurance, 48% complained to the FSP, and 25% of those who complained got a resolution. Of the 75% who did not get redress, none escalated to the Insurance Ombudsman.

Insert Table 6 here.

Table 6 summarises the differences between the number of complaints we see at the regulator vs. the number of complaints that remain hidden in the three sectors. Out of every 100 people who have a banking related grievance, 55 complain to the financial firm. Out of these, 21 continue to have a problem as their complaints do not get resolved at the FSP. Only 1 person out of the 21 complaints to the Ombudsman. This gives us a total of 65 grievances that either do not translate into complaints even to the FSP (45 out of the 100),

⁶Figure A.5 in the Appendix presents in detail the types of grievances faced by users of banking, payments and insurance products.

or do not get lodged with the Ombudsman (20 out of the 21). For every 1 banking related complaint we see in the official statistics, there are 65 complaints that remain hidden. Similarly, for every one complaint we see on payments, 60 remain hidden, while 88 remain hidden in the case of insurance.

4.3 Understanding complaints behaviour

We evaluate if consumers who would complain in a hypothetical scenario complain to a greater extent in reality. We measure their intention to complain with the use of a “hypothetical scenario of an aggrieved bank customer”. Such a scenario was given to each survey participant, and participants were asked if they would take any of the possible actions if faced with the scenario. For example, one scenario reads as follows:

Rahul opened a bank account with a private bank six months ago. One day while inspecting his passbook, he sees that Rs X has been deducted from his balance towards “ATM withdrawal charges”. He was informed at the time of account opening that the Bank offers an unlimited withdrawal facility from its own ATMs and he had always withdrawn cash only from that Bank’s ATM. His family advised him to let go as he was a new customer.

If you were in Rahul’s place, what would be your preferred course of action?

The options provided included taking public action (such as filing complaint at bank, going to the RBI, going to consumer courts), or taking private action (such as stop using the ATM card or the bank). We find that the intention to take public action at the occurrence of grievance is very high. 93% of the respondents said that they would have take some kind of public action, while 37% reported that they will stop using the ATM if they faced issue, while 32% said that they would change their bank if faced with an issue with ATM.

However, we find that people’s responses in the hypothetical scenario do not correspond to their actual behaviour. Of those who had said they would complain to either the FSP, Ombudsman, or the court in the hypothetical scenario, only 50% actually make a complaint when faced with a grievance. This counterfactual suggests that process frictions generate a wedge between a consumer’s intent and actual behaviour observed when faced with a grievance.

4.4 Type of grievance and complaints

Table 7 presents an analysis of the subset of those individuals who had a grievance but chose to not complain. We categorise the type of grievance (transaction, or non-transaction), with the reason that people give for not lodging a complaint. For grievances related to transaction failures we find that most people don't complain because they think that it is a small problem. On the other hand, for grievances related to non-transactions, fewer people think that the problem is small, but are deterred largely because they think that resolution is unlikely.

Insert Table 7 here.

These numbers are consistent with the results in the previous sections - most non transaction grievances are insurance related, and the two main reasons for not complaining in the case of insurance are that the process is unknown, or resolution is unlikely.

5 Results

Table 8 presents the odds ratio from a logistic regression presenting the correlates of socio-economic characteristics with the incidence of grievances and complaints. The question of interest is whether a certain category of people is more likely to face problems in their use of banking, payments and insurance products. Conditional on facing a problem, who is more likely to access the formal redress system?

Insert Table 8 here

We find that those that are in the 31-40 and 41-54 age groups more likely to face grievances and more likely to complain, relative to those in the 21-30 age groups. As one gets older, one is less likely to have grievances, and less likely to complain. This could be because of two reasons: either the old are more experienced with products and hence less likely to get into contracts they don't understand. It could also be that the young are more vocal about problems, and hence more likely to say that they have a problem.

Education matters for grievances and complaints. Those who are illiterate, or have some schooling are less likely to face a grievance relative to those who have a college degree. This is an important finding especially in light of the financial inclusion drive in India where large number of not well educated people are entering financial markets. Similar results show up for income and assets. The higher the family income the larger are the odds of

facing a grievance and complaining. In the case of assets, the highest asset quintile has lower odds of facing a grievance, but higher odds of complaining relative to the lowest asset quintile. Controlling for all individual characteristics, the type of grievance doesn't matter for complain behaviour suggesting that designs of grievance systems should be centered around household behaviour rather than around financial products.

We turn next to studying predicted probabilities of complain behaviour. Table 9 presents the results.

Insert Table 9 here

Vulnerable groups, as defined by low income, low assets and low education have the lowest probability of complaining conditional on having a grievance. The probability of complaints by someone who is illiterate and in the lowest asset and income quintile is 0.35. If a person in the same income and asset quintile has a graduate degree, then the probability jumps to 0.47. In fact, our results suggest that education matters more than assets. There is a difference of almost 10 percentage points between someone who is illiterate, with high assets and in the first income quintile and someone who graduate, with Low assets in the same income quintile.

5.1 Why do financial consumers choose not to complain?

Why do individuals not complain when faced with a problem? There may be several reasons. First, the individual may think that the problem is trivial, or not even valid, or that the problem will get resolved in a couple of days by itself. We term these set of responses as “small problem”. Second, the individual may not have adequate information about existence of a complaints mechanism, or not know how to access it. We term this “unknown process”. A third reason that we term as “costly process” would include responses that suggest that the process is costly and hence a deterrent to complaining. Finally, the respondent may think that there was no point in complaining because there is no possibility of a resolution. We term this as “resolution unlikely”. Given the low levels of resolution both by the FSP and the Ombudsman (especially in insurance and banking), one would expect that the top reason for not complaining would be low expectation of resolution.

Insert Figure 1 here

Figure 1 presents the main reasons why people do not complain when faced with a griev-

ance. The reasons vary depending on the product in question. In the case of payments, the biggest reason for not complaining is the perception that the problem is small (or will get resolved on its own), while in the case of banking it is the cumbersome nature of the process, while in insurance it is that the process is not known. There are third things that stand out. First, one of the biggest frictions for not complaining is the information gap. Even for banking and payments, where “unknown process” was not the main reason for not complaining, as many as 28% and 18% respondents provided this as their reason. Financial service providers and regulators need to improve their communication about the complaints process. Second, the process of redress in insurance needs an overhaul. Either people do not know the process, or if they do, they think that no resolution is possible. This suggests that confidence in the insurance system is much lower than in banking and payments. Third, both banking and payments grievance redress systems need to think about reducing the costs of complaining.

Insert Table 10 here

Insert Table 11 here

While the unconditional estimates of the reasons for not complaining paints a clear picture, we approach this more formally to understand whether vulnerable groups face a different combination of reasons why they may choose not to complain.

Table 10 presents these results formally with a regression. We define a dummy variable to take the value 1 when an individual is considered vulnerable (low assets, income, education) and 0 otherwise. Column 1 of Table 10 shows that the vulnerable group, in comparison to the non-vulnerable group, are 5.5 percentage points less likely to face a grievance with financial products. While an array of reasons such as less frequent use of products is not uncommon to drive this incidence of a problem, we find that conditional on facing a problem (Column 2), vulnerable groups are about 12 percentage points less likely to complain than the non-vulnerable ones, despite the level of complaint likelihood for the non-vulnerable group being only 53%. This difference is statistically and economically large and significant.

Table 11 explores further the reasons behind why vulnerable groups may choose not to complain. We find that the underlying reasons why non-vulnerable group do not complain is different from those of the vulnerable groups. First, all individuals in our survey hold a strong belief that resolution is unlikely and this is no different between the two groups.

Second, vulnerable groups find it difficult to complain because of unknown process more than the rest. This difference is economically large and significant. Finally, non-vulnerable groups typically find these problems to be small and insufficient to pay the high cost of complaining.

6 Policy Suggestions

India has seen a massive increase in the “banked population” in recent years. To convert the use of bank accounts into more meaningful participation in financial markets may require further reforms, especially to enable trust and provide swift resolution to grievances faced by Indian households.

In this paper, we present results from a representative phone survey that measures consumer grievances in retail financial markets. We find that for every complaint on banking and payments that makes it to the regulatory system, there are 60 grievances that do not get voiced. In insurance the number is 80 grievances for every official complaint. Grievances in banking and payment mostly pertain to “transaction issues” such as delays in payments, and malfunctioning of the technology. Grievances in insurance often pertain to “non transaction issues” such as mis-selling and fraud. There are a number of frictions in the process of voicing complaints - ranging from limited information about the process, to limited faith that a resolution is even possible. Those in vulnerable groups (with low education and low assets) are less likely to voice their complaints, and more likely to not have enough information about the redress procedure.

Our results suggest that current systems are not able to offer relief to consumers. Poor experience with markets, either for themselves, or those in the social network is sufficient to result in inefficient use of financial markets. A “flight to safety” in this context would be to revert to traditional means of investing, namely physical assets in the form of land, housing and gold.

Our results suggest that policymakers at the very minimum consider the following principles in the design of a modern, inclusive grievance redress framework. First, there is a need for robust processes in the area of grievance redressal, especially for the poor and less educated – a consumer-centered design of resolving grievances that are not product-specific. What is striking is that many of these people are not aware of the process for making complaints. Solving the information constraint is a low hanging fruit for policymakers.

Financial inclusion movement started 20 years ago to get poor people included. The movement needs to turn towards gearing the internal plumbing of the financial system to cater to the new class of customers onboarded into the system. Building trust in using formal financial services with a robust GRM will enable sustained use of formal financial services, thus resulting in a more formalised financial economy.

Acknowledgments

Declaration of interest statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare

References

- Ayers, I., Lingwall, J., & Steinway, S. (2014). Skeletons in the database: An early analysis of the CFPB's consumer complaints. *Fordham Journal of Corporate and Financial Law*, 343–392.
- Balasubramaniam, V., Biswas, K., Sane, R., & Sarah, M. A. (2020). Estimating customer complaints using twitter feeds. *The Leap Blog*, 14 May 2020. <https://blog.theleapjournal.org/2020/05/estimating-customer-complaints-using.html>
- Balasubramaniam, V., Gawali, A., Sane, R., & Sharma, S. (2022). Examining grievances and redress for banking products. *The Leap Blog*, 28 December 2022. <https://blog.theleapjournal.org/2022/12/examining-grievances-and-redress-for.html#gsc.tab=0>
- Balasubramaniam, V., Sane, R., Sarah, M., & Suresh, K. (2022). Do Indian financial firms have a robust Grievance Redress Framework in place? *NIPFP Working Paper No. 365*. https://nipfp.org.in/media/medialibrary/2022/01/WP%5C_365%5C_2022.pdf
- Bose, U., Filomeni, S., & Mallick, S. (2021). Does bankruptcy law improve the fate of distressed firms? the role of credit channels. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 68, 101836.
- Cheng, J., Qian, W., & Reeb, D. M. (2016). Financial intermediaries and consumer complaints. <https://www.stern.nyu.edu/sites/default/files/assets/documents/Financial%5C%20Intermediaries%5C%20and%5C%20Consumer%5C%20Complaints%5C%20Sept%5C%202026.pdf>
- Coffey, D., Hathi, P., Khalid, N., & Thorat, A. (2021). Measurement of population mental health: Evidence from a mobile phone survey in india. *Health Policy and Planning*, 36(5), 606–619.
- Demirgüç-Kunt, A., Klapper, L., Singer, D., & Ansar, S. (2022). *The global index database 2021: Financial inclusion, digital payments, and resilience in the age of covid-19*. World Bank Publications.
- Doyle, M., Bondy, V., & C, H. (2014). The use of informal resolution approaches by ombudsmen in the UK and Ireland: A mapping study. *Project Report. Ombudsresearch, UK*. <https://ombudsmanresearch.files.wordpress.com/2014/10/the-use-of-informal-resolution-approaches-by-ombudsmen-in-the-uk-and-ireland-a-mapping-study-1.pdf>

- Ferran, E. (2012). Regulatory lessons from the Payment Protection Insurance mis-selling scandal in the UK. *European Business Organization Law Review*, 13, 247–270. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1566752912000171>
- Foohy, P. (2017). Calling on the CFPB for help: Telling stories and consumer protection. *Law and Contemporary Problems*, 80(3), 177–210.
- Gulati, K., & Suresh, K. (2022). Issues concerning Grievance Redress Mechanism (GRM) in Indian financial regulators. *NIPFP Working Paper Series, No 364*. https://www.nipfp.org.in/media/medialibrary/2022/01/WP%5C_364%5C_2022.pdf
- Heese, J., & Pérez-Cavazos, G. (2021). The effect of retaliation costs on employee whistleblowing. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 71(2-3), 101385. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacceco.2020.101385>
- Kruks-Wisner, G. (2018). The pursuit of social welfare citizen claim-making in rural India. *World Politics*, 70(1), 122–163.
- Littwin, A. (2015). Why process complaints: Then and now. *Temple Law Review*, 87(4), 895–946.
- Morgan, P. J., & Long, T. Q. (2020). Financial literacy, financial inclusion, and savings behavior in laos. *Journal of Asian Economics*, 68, 101197.
- Raghavan, M., & Shah, S. (2020). Fix the problems in aadhaar-based cash transactions. *LiveMint*, 8 May 2020. <https://www.livemint.com/opinion/columns/fix-the-problems-in-aadhaar-based-cash-transactions-11588930862806.html>
- Robinson, N. (2015). Closing the implementation gap: Grievance redress and India’s social welfare programs. *Columbia Journal of Transnational Law*, 53(2), 321–362. <https://heinonline.org/HOL/P?h=hein.journals/cjtl53&i=327>
- Sane, R., Sharma, S., & Suresh, K. (2021). Grievance redress in the financial sector in india: Lessons from the field. *The Leap Blog*, 26 February 2021. <https://blog.theleapjournal.org/2021/02/grievance-redress-in-financial-sector.html>
- Sharan, M., & Kumar, C. (2019). Something to complain about: How minority representatives overcome ethnic barriers. https://scholar.harvard.edu/files/mrsharan/files/something%5C_to%5C_complain%5C_kumar%5C_sharan%5C_ethnic%5C_div%5C_3%5C_2.pdf

Appendix

Tables

Table 1 Reported Statistics of Incidence of Grievances

This table documents the number of grievances received by sectoral regulators at all India level. In case of the insurance and the pensions sector, complaints data as received by centralised online portal (IGMS for insurance and CGMS for pensions) is also available. The incidence rate is calculated by dividing the total complaints by total population covered by the financial product. The data is sourced from annual reports (2019-2020) of the regulators.

Product	Regulator	Region	Level	Number of complaints received	Incidence (%)
Banking	RBI	All India	Ombudsman	195,901	0.01
Payments	RBI	All India	Ombudsman	NA*	NA
Insurance	IRDAI	All India	IGMS	165,217	0.04
			Ombudsman	13,285	0.004
Securities	SEBI	All India	Scores	55,526	0.1
Pensions	PFRDA	All India	CGMS	156,966	0.36
			Ombudsman	20	0.046

*Complaints registered at digital transactions ombudsman were 2481, but they do not capture complaints against third party UPI services

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics

The table provides the summary of the sample. It provides the distribution of age, household size, education level, occupation and family income. It also presents participation rates of different financial markets.

Variable	Number of observations	Percentage
Age		
21-30	2795	62 %
31-40	1039	23 %
41-54	525	12 %
55-64	141	3 %
65+	44	1 %
No. of family members		
1-2	343	8 %
3-5	2591	57 %
6-8	1230	27 %
9+	380	8 %
Highest education level		
Illiterate	352	8 %
Upper primary	497	11 %
Secondary	729	16 %
Senior secondary	1256	28 %
Graduate and above	1710	38 %
Annual family income		
Less than 1 lakh	1583	38 %
1-3 lakh	1812	44 %
3-6 lakh	517	12 %
6-10 lakh	136	3 %
Above 10 lakh	103	2 %
Occupation		
Private salaried job	2163	48 %
Self employed	800	18 %
Unemployed	723	16 %
Student	345	8 %
Government salaried job	125	3 %
Skilled daily-wage labor	148	3 %
Agricultural worker	103	2 %
Unskilled daily-wage labor	113	2 %
Retired	24	1 %
Access to financial products		
Banking	4404	97 %
Payments	2325	51 %
Insurance	925	20 %
Securities	227	5 %
Pensions	192	4 %

Table 3 Incidence and frequency of grievances

This table presents the incidence rates of grievances i.e total grievances as a percentage of the total users of product. It also presents the frequency of grievances i.e number of times a grievance with the financial product in a typical year.

	Banking	Payments	Insurance	Securities	Pensions
<hr/>					
Grievances					
N	397	405	37	14	5
%	9	17	4	6	3
<hr/>					
Freq					
1-2	249	179	27	10	
3-5	77	81	4	1	1
>5	71	145	6	3	4

Table 4 Consumer perception of the nature of grievances

The table describes the nature of grievances faced by consumers of banking, payments and insurance. “Transaction” related grievances includes delays or failures in all kinds of transactions. Category of “Non-transactions” involve instances of poor sales practices or outright fraud.

	Transaction	Non-transaction
Banking	97.27	2.73
Payments	99.24	0.76
Insurance	48.00	52.00

Table 5 The process of grievance redress

This table shows the experiences consumers of banking, payments and insurance had with grievance redress process. It presents the statistics on the lifecycle of a grievance : from owning the product to initiation of a grievance till the resolution by the ombudsman.

	(1) Own the product	(2) Had a Grievance	(3) Responded on complaints	(4) Complained to FSP	(5) Complaint resolved by FSP	(6) Complained to Ombudsman	(7) Resolved by Ombudsman
Banking	4404	388	256	140	88	3	0
Payments	2325	405	397	199	157	1	1
Insurance	925	37	25	12	3	0	NA

Table 6 Estimating the gap between official statistics and grievances

This table summarises the differences between the number of complaints we see at the regulator vs. the number of complaints that remain hidden in the three sectors. Being hidden means that grievances either do not translate into complaints even to the financial service provider or do not get lodged with the Ombudsman

	Official	Survey
Banking	1	65
Payments	1	60
Insurance	1	88

Table 7 Type of grievance and reasons for not complaining

This table categorise the type of grievance (transaction, or non-transaction), with the reason that people give for not lodging a complaint when faced with a grievance.

	%	
	Transaction	Non-transaction
Costly process	26.71	25.00
Resolution unlikely	15.75	41.67
Small problem	34.93	8.33
Unknown process	22.60	25.00

Table 8 Grievances and socio-economic characteristics

This table presents the odds ratio from a logistic regression on how socio-economic characteristics are correlated with the incidence of grievances and complaints. Column 1 presents regression results on probability of having a grievance while Column 2 presents regression results on probability of filing a complaint. Standard errors are reported in paranthesis.

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>	
	have.problem	actual.complaint
	(1)	(2)
age group: 31-40	1.040*** (0.108)	1.333*** (0.211)
age group: 41-54	0.787*** (0.155)	2.152*** (0.317)
age.group: 55+	0.595** (0.283)	0.553 (0.586)
educ: Illiterate	0.465** (0.234)	0.603 (0.488)
educ: Some schooling	0.754*** (0.100)	0.937*** (0.191)
family.income: 1-3 lakh	1.022*** (0.110)	1.437*** (0.209)
family.income: 3-6 lakh	1.403*** (0.154)	1.531*** (0.282)
family.income: 6-10 lakh	1.595*** (0.241)	1.688*** (0.439)
family.income: Above 10 lakh	2.840*** (0.246)	1.419*** (0.418)
occ1: Daily wage	1.046** (0.440)	0.758 (0.899)
occ1: Not earning	1.287*** (0.389)	1.486* (0.773)
occ1: Salaried job	1.683*** (0.381)	1.489** (0.759)
occ1: Self employed	1.847*** (0.390)	1.866** (0.775)
quintile_asst 2:	0.936*** (0.155)	1.064*** (0.299)
quintile_asst 3:	0.893*** (0.161)	1.160*** (0.307)
quintile_asst 4:	1.106*** (0.161)	1.399*** (0.307)
quintile_asst 5:	0.972*** (0.175)	1.125*** (0.321)
household.size: 3-5	0.897*** (0.175)	0.682** (0.334)
household.size: 6-8	0.934*** (0.187)	1.260*** (0.361)
household.size: 9+	1.591*** (0.214)	0.990** (0.397)
typeofgrievance: non-transaction		0.802 (0.500)
Constant	0.132 (0.427)	0.509 (0.855)
Observations	4,150	616
Log Likelihood	-1,688.142	-408.114

Table 9 Predicted probabilities for complaint behaviour

This table presents the predicted probability of complaint for various categories of family income, education and assets. The other variables include age group of 41-54, household size of 3-5, with a salaried job and non-transaction related grievance.

	Income				
	1	2	3	4	5
Illiterate, Low assets	0.35	0.44	0.45	0.47	0.43
Illiterate, High assets	0.37	0.46	0.48	0.51	0.46
Graduate, Low assets	0.47	0.56	0.58	0.60	0.56
Graduate, High assets	0.50	0.59	0.60	0.63	0.58

Table 10 Incidence of Problems and Complaint Action by Vulnerability

This table presents a regression estimate of the likelihood that vulnerable population face problems (Column 1) and when they face problems, whether they complain (Column 2).

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>	
	I(Have Problem = 1)	I(Complain = 1)
	(1)	(2)
Vulnerable Group	-0.055*** (0.013)	-0.118** (0.052)
Constant	0.163*** (0.006)	0.538*** (0.021)
Observations	4,543	681
R ²	0.004	0.008
Adjusted R ²	0.004	0.006
<i>Note:</i>	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01	

Table 11 Why do vulnerable groups not complain?

This table presents a test of mean difference between Vulnerable and Non-vulnerable groups in our sample by their reasons for not complaining when faced with a problem.

	Vulnerable	Non-vulnerable	Mean Difference
Costly process	0.14	0.23	-0.14**
Resolution unlikely	0.23	0.24	0.01
Small problem	0.11	0.23	-0.12***
Unknown process	0.36	0.23	0.13**
<i>Note:</i>	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01		

Table A.I Description of survey instrument

This table briefly describes the contents of the six modules the survey instrument.

No	Module	Description
1	Intention to complaint	Hypothetical scenario of aggrieved bank customer to illicit consumer response to grievance
2	Awareness on regulators and GRM	Ever heard of five regulators and existing GRM
3	Usage of financial products and incidence of grievances	Extent of usage, incidence and frequency of grievance with five financial products
4	Observed complaint behaviour	Response to grievances, reasons for not complaining
5	Experience with GRM	Five separate sections on experience with firm/regulator, impact on take up for each financial product
6	Demographics	Age, household size and composition, education, occupation, income and asset roaster

Table A.II Conditional probability of assignment of module 'X' given grievances is faced with a set of financial products 'P'

Module 'X'	Set of products with which grievance is faced (P)	Pr(X/ grievances with P)
X = Banking	P = {only Banking}	1
	P = {Banking and any combination of other financial products}	0
X = Payments	P = {Only Payments}, {Payments and Banking}	1
	P = {Payments and any other financial products except banking}	0.5
	P = {Payments and any combination of two products from Pensions, Securities and Insurance}	0.33
	P = {Payments, Insurance, Securities, Pension}, {All five products}	0.25
X = Insurance	P = {Only Insurance}, {Insurance and Banking}	1
	P = {Insurance and any other financial products except Banking}	0.5
	P = {Insurance and any combination of two products from Pensions, Securities and Payments}	0.33
	P = {Insurance, Payments, Securities, Pension}, {All five products}	0.25
X = Securities	P = {Only Securities}, {Securities and Banking}	1
	P = {Securities and any other financial products except Banking}	0.5
	P = {Securities and any combination of two products from Pensions, Insurance and Payments}	0.33
	P = {Securities, Insurance, Payments, Pension}, {All five products}	0.25
X = Pensions	P = {Only Pensions}, {Pensions and Banking}	1
	P = {Pension and any other financial product except Banking}	0.5
	P = {Pensions and any combination of two products from Securities, Insurance and Payments}	0.33
	P = {Pensions, Securities, Insurance, Payments}, {All five products}	0.25

Figures

Figure 1 Reasons for not complaining

This figure presents the main reasons why people do not complain when faced with a grievance in case of banking, payments and insurance.

Figure A.1 Sample v/s population distribution: Highest education level

This figure compares sample distribution of highest education with population estimates from the Consumer Pyramids Household Survey (CPHS) database for the same Delhi NCR region.

Highest Education level

■ Illiterate ■ Upper primary ■ Secondary
■ Senior secondary ■ Graduate and above

(a) Survey Sample Distribution

Highest Education level

■ Illiterate ■ Upper primary ■ Secondary
■ Senior secondary ■ Graduate and above

(b) CMIE CPHS Distribution

Figure A.2 Sample v/s population distribution: Household size

This figure compares sample distribution of household size, family annual income with population estimates from the Consumer Pyramids Household Survey (CPHS) database for the same Delhi NCR region.

Household size

1-2 3-5
6-8 9+

(a) Survey Sample Distribution

Household size

1-2 3-5 6-8 9+

(b) CMIE CPHS Distribution

Figure A.3 Sample v/s population distribution: Age group

This figure compares sample distribution of age with population estimates from the Consumer Pyramids Household Survey (CPHS) database for the same Delhi NCR region.

Age distribution

21-30 31-40 41-54
55-64 65+

(a) Survey Sample Distribution

Age distribution

21-30 31-40 41-54
55-64 65+

(b) CMIE CPHS Distribution

Figure A.4 Sample v/s population distribution: Annual family income

This figure compares sample distribution of family annual income with population estimates from the Consumer Pyramids Household Survey (CPHS) database for the same Delhi NCR region.

Family income (per annum)

■ Less than 1 lakh ■ 1-3 lakh ■ 3-6 lakh
■ 6-10 lakh ■ Above 10 lakh

(a) Survey Sample Distribution

Family income (per annum)

■ Less than 1 lakh ■ 1-3 lakh ■ 3-6 lakh
■ 6-10 lakh ■ Above 10 lakh

(b) CMIE CPHS Distribution

Figure A.5 Issues faced with financial products

This figure depicts the specific issue faced by consumers of banking, payments and insurance.

